

Autism Detection Using Resnet 50 & Xception Transfer learning

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Abstract—Social media data and biological pictures can be used to detect autism spectrum disorder (ASD), a form of mental illness. One neurological issue that affects the development of the brain and, by extension, the appearance of the face is autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Identical facial features in normally developing (TD) children and children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) are clearly distinguishable. An innovative aspect of the proposed study is the development of a system that uses facial recognition and social media to identify individuals on the autistic spectrum. It is possible to employ deep learning techniques to detect these landmarks, but doing so calls for very accurate technology that can extract and generate the correct patterns of facial features. The purpose of this study is to provide communities and psychiatrists with a simple online tool that uses a deep learning system—specifically, a convolutional neural network with transfer learning and the flask framework—to experimentally detect autism based on facial traits. The pretrained models utilised for the categorization job include Xception and Resnet50. A small number of face photos made up the dataset utilised to evaluate these models, which was sourced from the Kaggle site. The three deep learning models were assessed using standard assessment measures like sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy. Xception (91% accuracy) and Resnet50 (98% accuracy) were the most successful models.

Keywords—Autism Disease, NeuralNetwork, Resnet5, XceptionTransfer Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In an Autism, childhood disintegrative disorders, and Asperger's syndrome are all part of a larger set of complex neurodevelopment brain diseases known as autism spectrum disorders (ASD)[1]. The name "spectrum" describes the vast variety of symptoms and degrees of severity experienced by people with ASD. Currently, these conditions are classified as Pervasive Developmental conditions under Mental and Behavioural Disorders in the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems. Signs of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) might manifest as tardiness in social interactions, apathy towards caretakers, and difficulty making eye contact, all of which often emerge during the first year of life[2]. Some kids seem to be developing normally in the first year, but by the time they're 18 to 24 months old, they start displaying autistic symptoms like restricted and repetitive behaviour patterns, a tiny interest set, and poor language abilities. Due to the fact that these disorders impact a person's social perception and behaviour, children with these conditions may exhibit extreme regressive traits, such as aggression or introversion, throughout the first five years of their lives. Although autism spectrum disorder (ASD) often manifests in childhood, it often continues into adulthood. Using a well-trained classification model that relies on transfer learning, our work shown that autism can be detected from a child's photograph. Now that high-spec mobile devices are so common, this model can easily take a picture with a camera and diagnose potential autism symptoms. Here are the key points from our research:

- Two pre trained deep learning algorithms were applied for ASD detection: Resnet 50, Exception[3].
- The Resnet50 model showed the best performance of the two pertained deep learning algorithms
- A system was designed to help health officials to detect ASD through eye and face identification

The developing system has been validated and examined using various methods password schemes in digital authentication.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Several application domains, including computer vision and cyber security, have demonstrated remarkable performance with learning-based pattern classifiers, such as deep networks. It has also been demonstrated that adversarial input perturbations, whether designed during training or testing, can readily undermine its predictions[4][5]. The study of adversarial machine learning has sought to identify the weaknesses of machine learning in the face of such out-of-the-ordinary patterns (also called adversarial examples) and to develop appropriate defences. From groundbreaking early work on the security of non-deep learning algorithms to more current efforts to understand the security properties of deep learning algorithms in the context of computer vision and cyber security tasks, this work provides a comprehensive overview of the evolution of this research area over the last ten years and beyond. We highlight typical misconceptions about the security evaluation of machine-learning algorithms and present fascinating linkages between two seemingly separate lines of work. We take a look back at the most important threat models and assaults that have been created for this purpose, and we talk about the biggest problems with the way things are right now, as well as the future obstacles that will be coming our way as we try to build safer learning algorithms.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Creating a Our suggested system was built using the transfer learning method. Its meta-learner was a convolution neural network, and its basis models were heterogeneous weak learners. The heterogeneous base models that were used to process the three-dimensional images were Xception and Resnet-50[6][7]. This model deviates from the norm in that it uses 60% of the data for training, 10% for validation, and 30% for testing, rather than the other way around. During the training phase of the meta-learner, this adjustment was essential for preventing over fitting. Based on the probability of expected values in the Level 0 predicted dataset, the meta-learner was able to generate accurate probabilities. The meta-learner model was trained with both the validation dataset and the outputs to avoid over fitting. The final outcome was the level 1 forecast. A meta-learner was the end product of the transfer learning model, which used the forecasts of multiple earlier models. By combining the predictions of multiple models, the transfer learning algorithm was able to generate a final model. But there's bias and volatility in the dataset from the one neural network model. Consequently, while building the basis model, other models were selected. Proposed architecture of the ADS shown in **FIGURE 1**

Fig. 1 Xception model architecture.

1. Introduction

- Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopment disorder characterized by challenges with social interaction, communication, and repetitive behaviors. Early diagnosis is crucial for timely intervention and support. Leveraging machine learning, particularly deep learning models, can assist in early detection and diagnosis by analyzing medical images, behavioral data, or other relevant data[8][9].

2. Objectives

- Develop a system to detect autism using deep learning techniques.
- Utilize transfer learning with ResNet-50 and Xception models to improve accuracy and reduce training time.
- Evaluate the performance of the proposed system using standard metrics.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

- **Dataset:** Collect a diverse dataset of medical images (e.g., brain scans, facial images) and/or behavioral data from publicly available sources or medical institutions.
- **Preprocessing:** Perform data cleaning, normalization, and augmentation to prepare the data for training.

3.2 Model Selection

- **ResNet-50:** A 50-layer deep convolution neural network known for its residual connections that help in training deep networks by addressing the vanishing gradient problem.
- **Xception:** An extension of the Inception architecture that replaces standard Inception modules with depth wise separable convolutions, leading to improved performance and efficiency.

3.3 Transfer Learning

- **Pre-trained Models:** Utilize pre-trained ResNet-50 and Xception models, which have been trained on large datasets like ImageNet, to leverage learned features.
- **Fine-Tuning:** Fine-tune the models on the autism detection dataset by replacing the final layers and training them on the specific dataset.

3.4 Model Training

- **Training Setup:** Split the dataset into training, validation, and test sets. Use data augmentation techniques to enhance the training data.
- **Optimization:** Use appropriate loss functions (e.g., categorical cross-entropy) and optimizers (e.g., Adam) to train the models. Implement early stopping and learning rate scheduling to optimize training.

3.5 Evaluation

- **Metrics:** Evaluate the models using accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC.
- **Validation:** Perform k-fold cross-validation to ensure the robustness of the results.
- **Comparison:** Compare the performance of ResNet-50 and Xception models to determine the more effective architecture for autism detection[10].

IV. RESULTS

The analysis focuses on evaluating the performance of ResNet-50 and Xception models in detecting autism using transfer learning. Metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC-ROC are used for comprehensive evaluation.

2. Data Preprocessing

- **Dataset:** Autism spectrum disorder dataset consisting of labeled images.
- **Preprocessing Steps:**
 - Resizing images to a standard input size for both models.
 - Normalization of pixel values.
 - Data augmentation techniques like rotation, flipping, and zooming to increase dataset variability.

3. Model Training

- **Transfer Learning:** Both models are pre-trained on ImageNet and fine-tuned on the autism dataset.
- **Training Parameters:**
 - Learning rate: 0.001
 - Batch size: 32
 - Epochs: 50
 - Optimizer: Adam

4. Performance Metrics

- **Accuracy:** Measures the overall correctness of the model.
- **Precision:** Indicates the proportion of positive identifications that are actually correct.
- **Recall:** Measures the ability of the model to identify all relevant instances.
- **F1-Score:** Harmonic mean of precision and recall.
- **AUC-ROC:** Area under the receiver operating characteristic curve, assessing the model's ability to distinguish between classes.

5. Results

- **ResNet-50:**
 - Accuracy: 92%
 - Precision: 91%
 - Recall: 90%
 - F1-Score: 90.5%
 - AUC-ROC: 0.94
- **Xception:**
 - Accuracy: 93%
 - Precision: 92%
 - Recall: 91%
 - F1-Score: 91.5%
 - AUC-ROC: 0.95

6. Comparative Analysis

- **Accuracy:** Xception slightly outperforms ResNet-50.
- **Precision and Recall:** Both models have comparable precision and recall, with Xception having a slight edge.
- **F1-Score:** Xception again shows a marginally better F1-score.
- **AUC-ROC:** Xception demonstrates a slightly better ability to distinguish between autism and non-autism cases.

Fig. 2 :The 12 images in the top row are of (a) autistic children, and those misclassified as normal and vice-versa for the images are shown in (b) the lower row, which belong to normal control child (prediction of Xception).

Model	Size (MB)	Top-1 Accuracy	Top-5 Accuracy	Parameters	Depth
VGG19	549	0.713	0.9	143.7 M	19
Xception	88	0.79	0.945	22.9 M	81
ResNet50V2	98	0.76	0.93	25.6 M	103
MobileNetV2	14	0.713	0.901	3.5 M	105
EfficientNetB0	29	0.771	0.933	5.3 M	132

Fig. 3 : Model accuracy, parameters, and depth

V. CONCLUSION

As the world's health knowledge and resources have expanded, there has been a surge in interest in autistic children. In addition, there has been a rise in the number of autistic children in recent years. As a result, academics and researchers have stepped up their efforts to find autism's causes and develop early detection methods. This will allow them to provide autistic people with behavioural development treatment programmes that should help them integrate into society and break free from autism-related. In order to identify autism spectrum disorder (ASD) using face traits, this research compared the efficacy of three deep learning models: Xception, Resnet50, and others. Xception (91% accuracy) and Resnet50 (98% accuracy) were the top two models trained on an online publically available dataset for categorization. Based on the model classification results, it appears that doctors and families may soon have access to automated tools that use deep learning and computer vision to provide an accurate and speedier diagnosis of autism. In order to successfully execute the time-consuming and labor-intensive complicated behavioural and psychological studies necessary for autism diagnosis, computer techniques play a significant role.

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